

PROBLEMS OF THE SUPREME COURT'S REVIEW OF CASES IN THE INSTITUTION OF CASSATION AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

This article uses the comparative legal method to analyze the problems associated with the consideration of cases in the Supreme Court. In particular, among them are the problems associated with the postponement of cases and quality consideration of cases. And the ways of solving these problems are suggested.

Keywords: court, cassation, dispute, last instance, application of law

In recent years, the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan has undergone some changes. One of them was the introduction of the principle "one court - one instance". Based on this principle, cases heard in the first instance in inter-district and district (city) courts in civil cases must be heard in appeal only by regional and equivalent courts. Re-examination of cases heard in appeal instance shall be carried out by the Supreme Court in cassation instance.

In developed countries, the case review is formed as a 3-stage instance. That is, the Supreme Court acts as the last - the 3rd instance. In the current procedural legislation of Uzbekistan, the 3rd instance corresponds to the Supreme Court. Only, as the 4th instance, there is also the institute of reconsideration of cases in cassation. Below is a little discussion about the cassation instance, which is the 3rd instance. The purpose, objectives, and significance of this institution will be discussed. An attempt will also be made to shed light on problematic situations related to the review of cases in cassation instance.

A cassation appeal for review of a case in cassation instance shall be filed directly with the Judicial Board for Civil Cases of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan within one year from the date of the decision of the appellate court. The judge of the Supreme Court shall examine the cassation appeal within five days and render one of the decisions to refuse to accept the cassation appeal or to return it or to accept the cassation appeal for production and to accept the case for production. The decision to schedule a cassation appeal for judicial review shall be considered within a period of no more than one month from the date of its issuance. When considering a case in cassation instance, the court shall verify whether the rules of substantive law were correctly applied by the court of first and appellate instances, and whether the

requirements of procedural law on the materials in the case were observed. That is, in cassation instance, the judge does not examine the content of the case. He has no right to examine new evidence and establish new facts. Based on the results of the review of the case the judge shall be entitled not to satisfy the appeal, to partially or completely cancel the court documents and adopt a new decision, to change the court document, to cancel the court documents and to consider the case for a new review to the court.

The above has briefly described the procedure for consideration of cases in cassation instance on the basis of the procedural legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In any legal system, the activity of the Supreme Court has the following two purposes. The first purpose is individual and the second is public. The individual purpose of the Supreme Court meets the natural desire of the losing party to have the case heard by a higher court. Its public purpose is to control the activities of the lower courts, to unify the practice of law, and to develop the law. Today, this social purpose is of great importance. Because the principle of the rule of law requires that such cases are resolved on the basis of the same legal criteria and that these criteria be known in advance.

The Supreme Court's review of cases as a last instance also serves, to some extent, the two purposes noted above. When the Supreme Court reviews a case, it seeks to correct errors in the application of the law by lower courts. At the same time, the Supreme Court provides the general public with information about how to apply the law in the future.

One of the main problems of the Supreme Court in all legal systems is the large number of cases to be considered. That is, the inability to hear cases on time and the unreasonable postponement of cases, as well as problems related to the quality administration of justice by the Supreme Court. There are two ways to address these problems. First, by increasing the Supreme Court's ability to hear more cases, and second, by reducing the number of cases. The high courts' decision to choose one of these two solutions depends on several factors. In particular, factors such as an understanding of the caseload problem, national theories about Supreme Court appointments, a particular emphasis on the right to appeal court documents, budgetary constraints, and the severity of legal rules affect which of the above two different decisions to choose.

The Supreme Court is the court at the top of the pyramid of the judiciary, which makes the final decision on legal issues within the country and serves a variety of purposes. The rule of law requires that laws be applied equally to all. The Supreme Court acts as a beacon for lower courts in interpreting the law.

Supreme Court decisions, along with the elimination of ambiguities and gaps in the law, adapt legal rules to modern requirements. The Supreme Court has a key role to play in ensuring the accuracy of legal rules, the proper functioning of the justice system, and the functioning of the predictability function of legal rules.

The Supreme Court is the final link in overturning unjust judicial decisions. In general, Supreme Court review means focusing on errors in decisions made by lower courts. It is common for parties to agree that decisions they do not like should be reviewed and changed as erroneous decisions. As a result, the Supreme Court receives a large number of complaints from parties.

As a result, if there is no mechanism for the proportional sorting of these complaints, the number of cases to be heard by the Supreme Court will increase. The number of Supreme Court cases varies from country to country, depending on its judicial system. For example, for the U.S. Supreme Court, which hears 100-150 civil cases a year, 4,000 cases a year can be disastrous. By contrast, for the French Court of Cassation, which hears 22,000 civil cases a year, handling 4,000 cases a year means the court is dysfunctional.

Now there will be some discussion about solutions to the above problems. As stated earlier, the solutions to these problems can be divided into 2 large groups. 1) expanding the Supreme Court's ability to hear cases; 2) reducing the caseload;

Increasing the number of judges is one of the most commonly proposed solutions for increasing the Supreme Court's case review capacity. However, there are other measures that can have the same effect. For example, judges may be given additional support staff, and these staff members may be assigned some of the tasks that judges must perform. Others may recommend dividing the court into smaller sections or sections. In addition, procedural reforms may be introduced to speed up the case review process. For example, eliminating oral hearings, introducing different procedural processes depending on the type of case.

Regarding the problem of reducing the number of cases heard by the Supreme Court, comparative legal studies have devoted much attention to the mechanism of sorting cases. Important aspects of such a sorting mechanism include such aspects as the basis of sorting, the process of sorting, and whether this sorting is carried out by the lower court that issued the judgment or is carried out by the Supreme Court.

In addition to these two decisions, there are other measures. In some judicial systems, special attention is paid to measures to prevent cases from

being delayed. Even if the quality of justice suffers, it is important to try cases in a timely manner. In legal systems with a strong emphasis on the right to appeal court decisions, it is very difficult to discuss a triage mechanism. In some legal systems, passing laws is required to organize judicial proceedings and change the rules of court procedure. And it happens very slowly.

On the contrary, if the Supreme Court can adopt these rules, making such changes is easier and faster. Budgetary constraints limit the Supreme Court's ability to increase the number of judges, assistants, and other staff, as well as to make reforms related to improving the court's structure.

It can be concluded from the above arguments that the main purpose and task of the Supreme Court is to ensure fair resolution of individual disputes, control over the activities of lower courts, and unification of law enforcement practice. But the main obstacle to achieving these goals in the activities of the Supreme Court is a large number of cases to be considered. The solution to this problem may vary depending on such factors as the legal system, legal culture, and the level of judges in each country.

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